

QUASI-STATIC ROLLER AND BALL TEST FOR COMPOSITE PLATES

I. Bartsch¹

¹Institute of Composite Structures and Adaptive Systems, German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Lilienthalplatz 7, 38108 Braunschweig
Email: ivonne.bartsch@dlr.de, web page: <http://www.dlr.de/fa/>

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this research is to find a suitable and lighter material for a Unit Load Device (ULD) baseplate, which is currently made of aluminum. ULDs are airfreight containers and pallets, which are used to transport any kind of cargo by airplane. To verify new materials for this application, a roller and ball test is required which is the key element of this investigation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The weight of ULDs should be kept as low as possible. Alternative materials have to undergo mandatory tests. A roller and ball test is described in general in valid specifications. For the conducted test, a steel ball and a steel roller are forced into the investigated plate. The allowed indentation depth is limited and is thus an indicator for whether the material is suitable for an ULD baseplate. The aim is to find a lighter substitute for the aluminum baseplate which passes the test. Several different materials were tested and compared to each other in this paper.

2 MOTIVATION

ULDs are used for the transportation of airfreight by airplane. Like in all fields of aerospace, the weight should be kept as low as possible. If the structural weight can be reduced, more freight can be transported. This is an important issue for their consumers and has a positive impact on the fuel consumption as well as CO₂-emissions. The reduction of CO₂-emissions is one aim of operators like Lufthansa Cargo (20 % less CO₂-emissions until 2020 [14]) or DHL (30 % reduction until 2020 [5]) and also global aerospace programs like Flightpath 2050 (50 % less CO₂-emissions until 2050 [3]). ULDs are moved solely on rollers and balls by hand or automatically.

Figure 1 shows a loaded cargo loading system (CLS) inside an airplane with its components. Balls are also part of it. Such CLS is not integrated in every airplane and occasionally only covers fractions of the cargo department. If the cargo department is too small for ULDs, the freight is loaded by hand (bulk cargo). The ULD capacity for several airplanes is given in [2].

Figure 1: left: Cargo Loading System (CLS) in an aircraft, right above roller, right below latch [13]

2 TEST SAMPLES

The references for the performed investigation are aluminum plates with a 4 mm and a 2,7 mm thickness, which are used in state-of-the-art baseplates of ULDs. All materials are shown in Table 1. Sandwich materials are known for their high bending stiffness as well as their lightweight properties. Aluminum baseplates of ULDs tend to bow during use. This is why sandwich materials were chosen first to be tested with the roller and ball test.

The Metawell[®] plates (number 3-6) were bought directly from the manufacturer Metawell[®]. Their dimensions are 210 x 297 mm. This material is a sandwich with aluminum face sheets and a core made of an aluminum wave. The company Saertex manufactured plates number 7 through 11, which are 180 x 180 mm each. The GFRP prepreg used in these plates has the product designation EHG250-68-37 [8] which is marketed by the company Gurit. For the plates with the CFRP face sheets, Hexply[®] 6376C-926-35% [11] has been used. The honeycomb cores were manufactured by the company Schütz, their product designation is Cormaster[®] C1 [4]. All cores have a constant thickness of 11 mm. Two different types were used. Firstly, Cormaster[®] C1 (-4,8-32) (specimen 7 and 9) and secondly Cormaster[®] C1 (-3,2-48) (specimen 8) [4]. Specimens 12 and 13 were manufactured by the company Kraiburg and are 225 x 142 mm. For these specimens the GFRP prepreg [10] and the EPDM¹ [7] are applied. Specimens 14-16 were manufactured in house at the DLR with varying material and they have a size of 200 x 200 mm. Where GFRP prepreg is applied, again EHG241-300-45 has been selected. Where CFRP-prepreg has been chosen, we applied [9] from the manufacturer Gurit. The elastomer layers are based on EVA² with the product name being HHZ1907/59 [6]. The diversity in dimensions does not influence the results of the tests.

Number	cluster	Material	Thickness [mm]
1	I	Aluminum (reference 1)	4
2		Aluminum (reference 2)	2,7
3	II	hl 10-03-10 hl/H6 (Metawell [®])	6
4		hl 10-03-05 hl/H10 (Metawell [®])	10
5		sf cc 08-03-05 hl/H10 (Metawell [®])	10
6		Alu hl 08-02-05 hl/H5,5 (Metawell [®])	5,5
7	III	[GFRP(0;0)s/Honeycomb/GFRP(0;0)s]	13,3
8		[CFRP(0;45)s/Honeycomb/CFRP(0;45)s]	12,5
9		[CFRP(0;45)s/Honeycomb/[CFRP(0;45)s]	13,2
10	IV	[CFFP[0;45]s/Balsa/CFFP[0;45]s]	22,1
11		[GFRP[0;45]s/Balsa/GFRP[0;45]s]	21,1
12	V	[[GFRP/EPDM]*6/UHMW-PE]	4,0
13		[[GFRP/EPDM]*6/GFRP]	5,1
14		[GFRP*2/EVA/[GFRP/EVA]*2/EVA]s	5,7
15		[[GFRP]*2/[EVA/GFRP]*3]s	4,9
16		[CFRP/[GFRP/EVA]*5/GFRP/CFRP]	5

Table 1: List of tested materials

3 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

In order to substitute the aluminum baseplate with another material, the new baseplate has to undergo mandatory tests. One of the required tests for ULDs is the so called roller and ball test. It is specified in general in the IATA³ ULD Regulations [12]. Figure 2 shows the set-up of the test. The

¹ ethylene propylene diene

² ethylene vinyl acetate

³ International Air Transport Association

diameter of ball and roller is 25,4 mm. The length of the roller is specified as 51 mm. These dimensions correspond to the dimensions of the roller and ball units of the CLS in the airplane, which are also given in aerospace regulations [12]. Both test bodies shall be made of steel. The force depends on the used test body. In case of a ball the test force is $F_B=4$ kN and in case of a roller the test force is $F_R=9$ kN. The maximum permanent indentation which is allowed after the test is 0,25 mm for the roller and 0,5 mm for the ball. More specifications are not made in this regulation. On this basis a test set up was derived in the Institute of Composite Structure and Adaptive Systems of the German Aerospace Center (DLR). The specimen, mostly with an edge length of 200 mm x 200 mm, is fully supported by the specimen platform. The test body is forced onto the surface of the specimen with the test force F and the velocity V of 2 mm/min. To identify the maximum remaining indentation after the test, optical measurements with the system GOM⁴ ATOS were conducted 24 h after testing. The time span was chosen because the elastomer layers show effects of relaxation, especially for specimens with elastomer layers. It was recognized, that the indentation of them was higher directly after testing, but stagnate one day after the test.

Figure 2: General test set-up

The test setup is derived from the boundary conditions which are depicted in Figure 3. The airfreight container (ULD) is completely loaded with cargo and stays on a CLS for the entire time. An even load distribution is assumed. The setup considers the scenario that the airfreight container is not moved on the CLS, which is equivalent to a quasi-static load scenario. A dynamic load scenario would include the movement of the airfreight container on the CLS.

Figure 3: Boundary conditions

The used test machine is a Zwick 1484 with a 20 kN force sensor, which belongs to the institute. The tests were conducted under international standard atmosphere (23 °C / 50 % relative humidity) [1].

⁴ Gesellschaft für Optische Messtechnik mbH

Figure 4: Ball test - set-up

During the test, the vertical distance traveled by the traverse and the corresponding loads were recorded, see Figure 5.

Figure 5: Diagram of tested specimen number seven with a ball

Figure 5 shows the diagram for the test series with the ball. For this material combination, 6 specimens were tested. An offset of 2 mm on the x-axis gives a better readability of the results. The face sheet fails first and upon failure of the core, the maximum load is reached. It is an example for a material combination, which collapses during testing.

Figure 6 shows exemplary the specimen number 7-1 after the test as well as the analysis of the damaged specimen with the help of the ATOS-system and the software GOM[®]-Inspect. When damages occurred they were visible to the human eye and also show up in the diagram in Figure 5 as distinct kinks.

The different colors in Figure 6 highlight the magnitude of the indentation depth of the tested specimen. Cracks of the face sheet are also visible in both figures. They occur on the edges of the roller and continue at an angle of 45 degrees to the roller axis. The cracks caused by the ball start in the center of this test body.

Other material combinations, especially those with elastic layers do not show visible damages of the face sheet, like on Figure 6.

Figure 6: Specimen (number 7-1), left: after test, right: optical measurement

4 RESULTS

The tested plates were compared by their surface weight and by the remaining depth of the dent from both test bodies. All material combinations are tested a minimum of three times, to enable a statistical evaluation.

As one can see in Figure 7, all tested specimens feature a lower weight per area than the aluminum reference 1 (4 mm aluminum plate, red horizontal line). In order to also substitute reference 2 (2,7 mm aluminum plate, yellow horizontal line) the material of specimens number 10, 14, 15 and 16 is not suitable because it features a higher weight per area than the reference.

Figure 7: Surface weight of all specimens

The permanent indentation depth for each specimen is determined with the help of optical measurements according to Figure 6. The origin for the measurement is the undisturbed surface of each specimen. The results are summarized in the next two figures and show mean values.

Figure 8: Maximum indentation ball test, all specimens

Figure 8 shows the maximum indentation of the ball test. As one can see, specimens 3 to 9 and specimen 11 have deeper permanent indentations than allowed, which is highlighted by the red line. These material combinations are not suitable. All of these specimens are sandwich materials. In this case the face sheets as well as core materials collapse under the test load, except specimen 10. The specimens with number 10 and 11 differ in their material of face sheets. The face sheets of specimen 10 consist of CFRP and those of specimen 11 are made of GFRP, their orientation of layup is the same. The results show, that stiffer face sheets result in smaller damages. Specimens 12 to 16 also passed the test, which are the materials with elastomer layers inside.

Figure 9: Maximum indentation roller test all specimen

Figure 9 shows the maximum permanent indentation of the roller test. Compared to the results of Figure 8, the depth which is caused by a ball is deeper (excluding specimen number 5) than the depth caused by a roller. The reason is that the force gets distributed by the length of the roller and is therefore less concentrated than for the ball. The position of the test body on the Metawell[®] sandwich (specimen 3 – 6) influenced the result of the test. When the roller penetrated the Metawell[®] sandwich between and parallel to the two wave peaks, the face sheet cracked. This resulted in a considerably deeper indentation than for another roller placement with respect to the wave peaks. An indentation of the specimens with number 10 and 12 to 16 is not measurable. These results are similar to the results of the ball test. That is why these specimens are suitable for a new ULD baseplate.

5 CONCLUSION

An indentation test for two different test bodies based on the IATA ULD Regulations has been derived.

Indentations caused by a roller are smaller than those caused by a ball test body, although the test force is higher (9 kN)

Plates with an integrated elastomer layer passed the roller and ball test with very little or no permanent indentation. Furthermore, the identified plates with a FRP elastomer layup feature less surface weight than the aluminum reference. Specimen number 14 has the smallest indentation of all tested specimens. However, this indentation depth of that specimen differs little with that of the other specimens with elastomer layers inside. Including the weight per area of Figure 7, specimen 16 is the best choice for a 4 mm and specimen 12 for a 2,7 mm baseplate.

Common sandwich materials were found not to be suitable for the investigated application. The punctual loads which occurred in the test were too high for the face sheets. Material combinations made of FRP and elastomers show significantly better results.

To certify such a new material for a ULD baseplate, more tests like a burning rate test are necessary.

More tests which investigate the influence of elastomer layers in a FRV layup are planned.

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